

Microemulsion-microwave synthesis of template free zeolite and its application for the sorption of toxic metal ions

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Abstract : Present study includes synthesis of zeolite nanocrystals by microwave technique. Microwave heating has the advantage of short reaction time, producing small particles with narrow size distribution and high purity. Microemulsion-microwave method has been used to control zeolite crystal morphologies. Here we report a method to prepare uniform and smaller template-free zeolite nanocrystals in reverse microemulsion by microwave heating. TPA (tetrapropylammonium) was used as template, CTAB (cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide) and *n*-butanol were used as a surfactant and co-surfactant and cyclohexane as the oil phase. The synthesized powder was characterized by using different techniques such as X-ray diffraction, Transmission Electron Microscopy and FTIR analysis. Sorption study was carried out by batch method. Concentration of respective metal ions in solution was determined by UV-Visible spectrophotometer. MINTEQ A2 (Version 1.50) program has been used for carrying out the aqueous speciation of the metal ions.

Keywords : Microwave synthesis, CTAB, TPAOH, sorbent concentration, MINTEQ A2.

Introduction

There is considerable interest in the synthesis of zeolite because they can serve as model systems for the fundamental study of zeolite nucleation and crystal growth¹. Due to the microporosity, zeolites have very high surface area and have wide applications in catalysis, ion exchange separation and fuel cells²⁻⁴. These properties enable zeolites to be widely used as catalyst in petrochemical processing. In most of the synthesis organic template or structure directing agents (SDA) are used and the colloidal crystals obtained contain organic template in their void spaces. The template approach has several drawbacks. First, removal of template is normally carried out by calcination which leads to irreversible aggregation of the nanocrystal. Second, the use of template in synthesis tends to change the Si/Al ratio of the final product that could drastically affect their application (e.g. air separation). Synthesized zeolites by using template (tetramethylammonium) has Si/Al ratio greater than 1 and as a result, Na⁺ exchange, it has a pore size larger than 4 Å^{5,6}. In contrast, template free synthesis leads to Si/Al ratio as 1 and zeolite has pore size 4 Å after Na⁺ exchange. The slight change in pore size impacts the air separation capability of zeolite dramatically⁷. Last, template is expen-

sive. Thus synthesis of zeolite nanocrystals with small uniform diameter and without the use of template is highly desirable. Zeolites are industrially manufactured with micron-sized crystals or crystal aggregates. Recently, there have been efforts to synthesize nanocrystalline zeolites with crystal size less than 100 nm⁸⁻¹⁰.

Microwave heating has found a number of applications in synthetic chemistry¹¹. Microemulsion-microwave method has been used to control zeolite crystal morphologies¹². Under appropriate conditions, a variety of reactants can be introduced into the nanometer sized aqueous domains for reaction, leading to materials with controlled size and shape.

The use of zeolite materials for the environment protection is stimulated by good physicochemical properties such as selective sorption, non toxic nature, availability and low cost. Zeolites are also used in the field of waste water purification at trace level (at ppt level) for the removal of metal ions at ~10⁻¹² M. Sorption of metal ions on zeolite depends upon the characteristics of the metal ions (oxidation state, ionic potential etc.) and material (size and shape). Wide role of natural zeolites including water purification with the emphasis on the heavy metal

removal¹³, specially removal of Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} from waste water is most efficient at lower concentrations using different zeolites.

Results and discussion

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns as given in Fig. 1 for different samples produced using colloidal silica under different crystallization conditions (different shaking conditions and crystallization times) clearly indicate that the diffraction peak width and intensities of the synthesized samples greatly depend on the crystallization condition. Crystallization at 75 °C for 20 and 40 min with no shaking or stirring gave the sharp peak which inturn indicates crystalline nature of the materials. The XRD peak intensity increased with further increase of heating time. The corresponding crystal morphologies of these samples

(a)

Fig. 1. XRD of synthesized material for (a) 20 min and (b) 40 min.

are shown in Fig. 1. Consistent with XRD, samples appear to be crystalline with very uniform size with the increase of heating time from 20 to 40 min.

Material was further characterized by FT-IR spectroscopy (Shimadzu spectrophotometer), in which two bands were observed. The stretching bands at $\sim 1083\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 779 cm^{-1} are due to Si-O-Si and Al-O-Al respectively. Second, a new broad band below 1500 cm^{-1} can reasonably be assigned to the (N-H) deformation, vibration for amino salts appear as strong bands at $1600\text{--}1575\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and also near 1500 cm^{-1} . This suggests the absence of N-H linkage ($\sim 1616\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in template free-zeolites. TEM image confirms that zeolite nanocrystals from microwave heating are highly crystalline and have a narrow particle size distribution about 50 nm in size. It is believed that microwave heating offers faster and more uniform heating and thus leads to more uniform generation and growth of nuclei and avoids the formation of impurity phases.

Sorption study was carried out by batch method. Concentration of respective metal ions in solution was determined by UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Estimation of metal ions was carried out by using dithiozone as a color complexing agent. Lead ions are made to react with dithiozone at pH 4.0 to form a red colored complex lead dithiozonate, which is soluble in chloroform and measured using spectrophotometer at wavelength 510 nm. Zinc ions react with dithiozone to form a pink colored complex, which is extracted in to chloroform and was measured at 531 nm. Percentage sorption was determined by taking the concentration of metal ions in the suspension before and after sorption. Study includes kinetics, effect of pH on sorption as well effect of sorbent concentration.

Sorption of heavy metal ions on synthetic zeolites was carried out using batch method. Fig. 2 show kinetic study of the metal ions sorption on synthesized zeolites. From

Fig. 2. Kinetics for sorption of Pb^{2+} on zeolite.

figure it can be clearly seen that 12 h is sufficient for the saturation. For further study the time of equilibration was taken as 12 h. The sorption of metal ions as a function of pH in Fig. 3. The maximum sorption of Pb^{2+} on synthesized material was found at pH 5 after words it

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on sorption of Pb^{2+} and Zn^{2+} on zeolite

decreases with increasing pH (to 10). The maximum sorption of Zn^{2+} on synthesized material was found at pH 7 after words it decreases with increasing pH. Fig. 4 shows effect of sorbent dose (synthesized zeolite) variation on

Fig. 4. Effect of sorbent dose on sorption of Zn^{2+} on zeolite.

the sorption of metal ions. The sorption was observed to be enhanced with increase in sorbent dose which may be due to increase in numbers of surface sites into the suspension by increasing sorbent dose.

Percentage sorption and K_d values were calculated as :

$$\% \text{ Sorption} = [(C_1 - C_e)/C_1] \times 100$$

where, C_1 and C_e are the metal ion concentration before and at equilibrium.

$$K_d = [(C_1 - C_e)/C_e] \times V/m \text{ (ml/g)}$$

where V is the volume of the solution (ml) and m is the weight of the adsorbent (g).

The chemical form in which the metal ions are present

may further affect the sorption behavior. To investigate this behavior MINTEQA2 software of version 1.50 (Allison Geosciences) is used. Speciation has been carried out under normal simulated condition that is at zero ionic strength and at different pH (1-10) which was nearly meeting with the experimental conditions. From the speciation in Fig. 5 it can be clearly seen that the dominating species at initial pH 1 and upto pH 7 are their cationic

Fig. 5. Speciation of metal ions ($\sim 2 \times 10^{-2} M$) under normal environmental condition at zero ionic strength simulated using MINTEQA2

form that is Zn^{2+} and Pb^{2+} . The formation of hydrolyzed species has also been observed but in a very low concentration after pH 7. This behavior may be due to the low complexing tendency of the metal ions. The main hydrolyzed species observed are $Zn(OH)^+$, $Zn(OH)_2$, $Zn(OH)_3^-$ and $Zn(OH)_4^{2-}$ as well as $Pb(OH)^+$, $Pb(OH)_2$, $Pb(OH)_4^{2-}$ and $Pb_4(OH)_4^{4+}$ respectively for zinc and lead. The lower concentration of hydrolyzed species confirms

that the sorbing species at entire pH range are cationic form of the metal ions.

Experimental

Zeolite, $5.5\text{Na}_2\text{O} : 2.7\text{SiO}_2 : 1.0\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 160\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was synthesized by microwave method. The silica and alumina sources used were silica (CDH) and sodium aluminate (Riedel-dehaen). Sodium hydroxide (Merck) used as alkali source and template TPAOH. Weighed amounts of DD H_2O , sodium hydroxide, and sodium aluminate (NaAlO_2) were added, in that order and stirred vigorously until the solution became clear. Aqueous colloidal silica was added to complete the solution. The final reaction mixture was aged for 24 h before being transferred in to 250 ml polypropylene bottle containing a magnetic stirrer bar and was washed with DD H_2O under ultrasonication. The synthesized gel was sealed and aged overnight at room temperature with vigorous stirring.

Microemulsion was prepared by solubilizing the synthetic gel prepared above into a mixture of cyclohexane/CTAB and *n*-butanol/CTAB and was 130 and 10 respectively. The heating temperature of all the experiments was 75 °C. Microwave heating was carried out in a microwave oven with Teflon – lined stainless steel pressure vessel (PARR, 302 AC-T 304-073099). The heating profile was from room temperature to 75 °C within 20 and 40 min and then at 75 °C for a controlled amount of time without stirring. The maximum power output of the microwave was adjusted to 560 W. For all of the experiments, the product was first cooled to room temperature. All samples were washed by three repetitions of centrifugation with relative centrifuge at 14000 rpm for 30 min, then decanting, and redispersion in ethanol and water

with ultrasonication and the product was then dried at room temperature for 24 h and calcined at 500 °C for 4 h.

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